

COMPOSITION OF BOILED OIL.

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Boiled oil has been shown to have Diene value indicating the presence of conjugated double bond. The development of the conjugated state has been connected with the presence of metals in the finely divided condition. The formation of isooleic acid during the hydrogenation of oil has been ascribed to the presence of finely divided metals acting as catalysts through the first creation of conjugated state in the linolic acid residue and then to partial hydrogenation of the latter.

It is well known that linseed oil dries quicker in contact with metallic driers than it does by itself and the nature of drier, temperature, humidity and nature of light exercise a profound influence in the drying process. Polymerisation, oxidation and decomposition, sometimes simultaneous and sometimes in stages, occur with the result that finally we get the linoxyn skin (Woll, *Farben-Ztg.*, 1921, 26, 2851; Friend, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 162; Genthe, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1906, 19, 2087; Sabin, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1911, 3, 84; De Waeb, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1920, 39, 49). The time of drying is further shortened if instead of raw oil we take boiled oil i.e., linseed oil blown with air, which gives the appearance of boiling, in contact with catalysts, technically known as driers at 100-200°—the temperature depending on the drier used. (Rhodes and Wirt, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1923, 15, 1135; 1924, 16, 960; Fokin and Eibner, *Chem. Umschau*, 1925, 32, 97; Mackay and Ingle, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1917, 36, 319).

During boiling there is always slight decomposition of glyceride and the notable changes consist in the reduction of iodine value and the refractive index. The present enquiry is confined to the chemical change if any, in the composition of linseed oil during "boiling" which is responsible for the acceleration in the time of its drying and for the matter of that, to that change in the oil which is responsible for the polymerisation, oxidation and decomposition already referred to. One of us (Goswami, *Science & Culture*, 1935, 1, 283) had put forward views regarding such change. They are briefly the following :—

- (a) There is transference of double bonds to conjugated state in the unsaturated fatty acid residues (*cf.* Kappelmeier, *Farben-Ztg.*, 1933, 38, 77, 1018).
- (b) There is formation of hydroxy fatty acid glyceride.

- (c) There is fresh creation of double bonds in such hydroxy compounds as a result of elimination of elements of water.
 (d) There is re-arrangement of double bonds of (c) to conjugated state and finally
 (e) these changes are due mainly to metals in the finely divided state derived from the unstable metallic salts used as catalysts.

For the purpose of our experiments we prepared boiled oil under the conditions of the technical practice with regulated supply of air at 125° using various kinds of catalysts in various proportions. We have been able to prove (a) and (e). A preliminary note regarding the above has been published (Goswami and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 116). We have taken help of the well known reaction of maleic anhydride with compounds containing conjugated double bond.

This reaction has already been applied in elucidating the constitution of eleostearic acid found in tung oil which dries faster than linseed oil when used alone owing to the presence of glyceride of the acid in the former oil. Thus eleostearic acid has been given the following formula :—

Kaufmann and Baltes (*Fett. Seifen*, 1936, 48, 93) have now evolved out a method based on this for the valuation of Tung oil which is always hopelessly adulterated and calculated maleic anhydride absorption value which they call Diene value, according to the following formula :—

$$\frac{a-b}{c} \times 1.269$$

where a = no. of c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH required to neutralise 10 c.c. of 1% solution of maleic anhydride in acetone in blank experiment ; b = number of c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH required to neutralise the excess of maleic anhydride which remains when the oil is treated with it in sealed tube ; c = wt. of oil in g.

We have taken advantage of this method in establishing the presence of conjugated double bonds in boiled linseed oil.* The results obtained are given in the form of curves (*vide* Fig. 1-6).

The results with finely divided nickel although not very promising, support the view that the finely divided metals are responsible for the shifting of double bonds in the creation of conjugated state in linseed oil. They also throw light on the mysterious formation of *isoleic acid* during the process of hydrogenation of oils in which finely divided nickel is used, presumably it is formed from the linolic acid residue according to the following way :

Hilditch and Vidyarthi (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1929, **A**, 122, 552) have made experiments to throw light on the subject. They hydrogenated methyl oleate in presence of nickel and showed the presence of *isoleic acid*. But the methyl oleate they took contained, as they themselves have mentioned, methyl linoleate so their view that the *isoleic acid* found in their experiments has been derived from oleic acid seems to be untenable. Their explanation of the formation is the following :

In view of the evidence of migration of double bonds induced by finely divided metals, it seems to us that our explanation is more plausible one.

Our object in undertaking the present work has been

- (1) to give a true picture of the chemical change which occurs when linseed oil is boiled,
- (2) to explore the possibility of converting non-drying and semi-drying oils into drying oils,
- (3) to bring the whole boiling operation as also the valuation of boiled oil under chemical control,
- (4) to find out the solution of the *isoleic acid* problem.

* Bruce and Denly (*Chem. Ind.*, 1937, 86, 937) have suggested after determining Diene value of blown linseed oil and hydroxylated oils according to Ellis and Jones' method (*Analyst*, 1936, 81, 812) that the value is affected by hydroxyl group. This aspect has been examined by Pelikan and Mikusch (*Oil and Soap* 1937, 14, 209) who have shown conclusively that the determination of Diene value by Kaufmann and Baltes' method (*loc. cit.*) is not affected by hydroxyl group whereas Ellis and Jones' method is defective in this respect.

FIG. 1.

0.2 % Nickel.

FIG. 2.

2% Nickel oleate.

FIG. 3.

2% Nickel.

FIG. 4.

2% Nickel rosinate.

FIG. 5.

2% Manganese oleate.

FIG. 6.

0.1% Nickel.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

The oil mixed with catalyst was taken in the round bottom flask. A regulated supply of air was drawn through the tube "T" which was connected with a gasometer by a suction pump. The tube "T" was connected at the

FIG. 7.

bottom of the flask only to have an efficient stirring, although a separate stirrer "S" was placed in the flask. The flask was placed in an oil-bath, the temperature of which was kept at 125°. Samples were drawn at every half an hour and their Diene values were found out in the following way. The oil was mixed with 1% solution of maleic anhydride and heated in a sealed tube for 20 hours; side by side a blank experiment in which the corresponding quantities of acetone solution of maleic anhydride were heated

in a sealed tube for the same time was made. Both the solutions were then titrated against standard alkali to find out the amount of maleic anhydride taken up by the oil and the Diene values were calculated according to Kaufmann's formula. The following results are obtained.

Catalyst,	P.C.	1	1	1½	2	2½	3	3½	4	4½	5
		hour.	hour.	hours.							
Mn-oleate	2	3.6	5.6	13.38	12.2	8.9	5.3	4.7	3.5	3.2	2.5
Ni. „	2	0.5	0.82	3	4.4	4.5	4.6	4.5	3.9	3.7	3.5
Ni-rosinate	2	3.9	4.7	4.7	4.8	4.9	6.4	6.4	6.8	6.1	6.1
Nickel	2	2.1	6.9	8.9	6.9	6.1	5.1	2.8	—	—	—
Nickel	0.2	5.5	6.1	7	8.9	6	5.2	4	—	—	—
Nickel	0.1	5.9	7.2	7.3	6.0	5.1	4.1	3.9	—	—	—

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